

**The Development of Emotional Regulation and Social Interaction in Autism Spectrum
Disorder: Exploring the Usage of Music Therapy and CBI**

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Abstract

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) displays significant challenges when facing emotional regulation (ER) and social interaction (SI), impacting individuals' daily functions and interactions with others. This study evaluated the effectiveness of integrating music therapy (MT) with cognitive behavioral interventions (CBI) to address these core areas in children with ASD. This was done through a mixed-method approach which was directed to two different intended audiences: music therapists who have had children with ASD as patients and parents of children with ASD. Quantitative data was gathered through likert-scale questions to measure perceived improvements, whereas qualitative data was gathered through open-ended questions and optional interviews, providing insight into experiences and observations from both parties. Participants were then divided into groups, where parents were grouped based on the type of therapy their child has undergone, while therapists were grouped according to whether they have incorporated CBI into their daily practice. Findings show a clear correspondence between CBI alongside MT and a positive impact on ER and SI in comparison to other approaches. This was most evident from the music therapist responses to factors of Structured Effectiveness (Q7), where the group CBI + MT (mean = 3.6) compared to the MT only group (mean = 2.8) scores a near 1-point difference on the likert scale, suggesting a change in current outcomes from a moderate to high improvement. These findings support the conclusion that CBI, when paired with MT, may lead to more consistent improvements in both ER and SI. Compared to MT or any other therapeutic foundations, this structured approach alongside CBI brings a more concentrated perspective towards autism and addresses the lack of diverse, effective therapies available. Through this integrated approach alongside perspectives of first-hand observers, this research

contributes to two key aspects affecting children with ASD, aiming to enhance developmental outcomes for each individual child.

Introduction

The current field of therapy offers a plethora of approaches to address diverse needs across individuals who are affected by physical, mental, emotional, or developmental challenges. From the possible combinations, music therapy (MT) and cognitive behavioral interventions (CBI) have proven to be effective procedures when addressing the needs of children diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), which is defined as, “a neurodevelopmental disorder ... in social communication, social interaction, and restricted and repetitive behaviors, interests, or activities” (Ruth et al., 2014, p.1). Music therapy, which is “a systematic process of intervention ... to promote health using musical experiences and relationships,” engages its patients through a variety of strategies, whether instrumentally, vocally, or through improvised techniques from these approaches, all of which foster the development and personal growth of patients in a therapeutically (Ruth et al., 2014, p.1). On the other hand, CBI is a term derived from cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), while including core principles from Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA). Generally, CBI is a process where patients are taught to be experts at their own emotions and behavior while reducing negative thoughts within a real-life setting (Dorsey, 2021, p.1).

The main goal of this study is to examine how combining music therapy with CBI can create an effective approach designed to support children with ASD. Although music therapy has a considerable reputation for its ability to engage its patients through creative activities, its shortcoming is in the overall framework, where it lacks a focus on behavioral challenges and helping patients keep and apply their skills long-term. This is where CBI plays the role of a support therapy, in which it would fill the gaps of what music therapy cannot do by building their long-term skills development and behavior management while guiding their patients throughout various procedures. Many sources within the field reached a positive consensus on how music

therapy with cognitive behavioral interventions can prove beneficial when supporting children with ASD. Nevertheless, the potential of this specific approach is spoken by Luqian Zhao, who is a graduate of the University of Leeds, mentioning how “studies should examine how the effectiveness of music therapy may vary based on different treatment methods” (Zhao et al., 2025, p.16). Brianna Applewhite, who is a part of the Department of Psychological Medicine, states how “[d]ue to different approaches used, there are no confirmatory studies available for any of the reported positive findings” (Applewhite et al., 2022, p.15). Together, these perspectives point to a clear conclusion: actively exploring and implementing diverse approaches is necessary to determine their effectiveness and how it can be a feasible solution for further research. Music therapy and CBI strengthen emotional regulation and social interaction while offering an integrated approach to support children diagnosed with ASD.

Literature Review

Emotional Regulation

To address the challenges of emotional regulation that children with ASD are facing, music therapy and CBI play a crucial role by providing different creative and structured procedures to manage and develop their emotions. This is endorsed by Sini-Tulli Siponkoski, a Doctor of Philosophy and graduate from the University of Helsinki, who notes how there was a “significant short-term improvement in mood and reduction in anxiety and depression symptoms” as well as “positive long-term changes in various mood state” (2022, p.4). This describes the importance of music therapy when associated with short and long-term actions. Music therapy and CBI play crucial roles when contributing to the development of emotional regulation in various methods and procedures. Specifically for children with ASD, music therapy

can be incorporated through methods such as active music-making, lyric analysis, and most particularly, through the improvisation of methods. In a study conducted by James Ruth, an improvised procedure was applied, focusing on the participants' understanding of four emotions (happiness, sadness, anger, and fear) by measuring their abilities to perceive and develop their own emotions while incorporating music therapy interventions to recognize changes progressively. This process involved the use of chosen music pieces and their own composition of music while incorporating lyric analysis to expand their emotions and the extent it can be displayed (p.10).

Although CBI is not incorporated into this example, CBI is known to address and resolve complications involving emotional regulations. While doing so, it monitors individual progression for procedural consistency to show substantial results. This signifies how CBI can work alongside music therapy without interfering with each other, as music therapy encourages emotional examination and improvement of memorization while CBI ensures consistency of progression and mechanisms to each individual. In correlation to the gap, this integrated approach shows a significant change in both short and long term behaviors while being able speak on the challenges connected to emotional regulation. Although this method is integrated specifically for children with ASD, it can be adapted for many alternative disorders while being able to prove effective.

Social Interaction

In addition to how music therapy and CBI can support the complications under emotional regulation, it has the ability to also contribute to social interactions through improvised methods while incorporating real-life scenarios. To resolve issues involving social interaction with children diagnosed with ASD, James Ruth used different improvised procedures to express the

variety of possibilities music therapy possesses. Under these circumstances, it began with “a procedure where inter-rater agreement between two raters was determined by using the study’s dependent variables to rate seven children who were not part of the study” (p.11). This information was used to determine the overall changes discerned before and after the results. To bring optimal results, the study used relational music therapy, which is “described as an approach where sessions were mainly client-led and improvised activities were used” (p.10). This method was fixed to strengthen their confidence, solely to improve communication and expression. This resulted in “a further analysis show[ing] a statistically significant improvement” (p.11).

An alternate perspective shows how CBI contributes to social interaction, which is displayed by Ning Wang, graduate of Southern Medical University. The study focused on analyzing anxiety through its effects and extent, which is relevant to any individual with ASD as it plays a big role in their difficulties when communicating. As a result, it states how “CBI adopted in this study has a significant effect in alleviating anxiety” (2023, p.8), emphasizing the potential it has to address children diagnosed with ASD. By incorporating structured procedures shown by each therapy individually, it can ensure consistency and substantial results without requiring an immense amount of work.

Integration of Music Therapy and CBI

Building on the two main challenges of emotional and communication difficulties, the integration of music therapy and CBI are one of the best approaches when addressing complications of children diagnosed with ASD. Despite the amount of potential this perspective brings, there are drawbacks to consider when undergoing these procedures. One example comes from Hans Petter Solli, who has been a music therapist for 15 years and was studying participants with psychosis, states “how music therapy made them feel more vital, uplifted,

joyful, hopeful, and motivated,” but even so were brought to the conclusion that “such aspects were linked to experiences of well-being (an increase of positive health) rather than to a reduction of negative symptoms” (2015, p.21). An alternate perspective comes from Wenqin Li, a graduate of Sichuan University, as the study states how “[t]he person and personality of the therapist can also be a problem” and how “[t]he therapist should be cognizant of potential risks ... such as legal and ethical matters that could impact clients” (2022, p.1). Since these limitations do not state any procedures that would lead to backlash or repercussions they showcase how music therapy and CBI is a reliable and beneficial option. At most, it would only present minor limitations but still proves to be a safe approach for children affected with ASD.

Conclusion

The integration of music therapy and CBI emphasize its potential to solve many complications, including emotional regulation and social interaction, overall showing its significance when supporting children diagnosed with ASD. The current literature speaks on the success music therapy has when addressing complications involving emotional regulation through innovative methods specifically for that scenario. On the other hand, CBI demonstrates its importance through its strategies used to solve key factors affecting individuals with ASD. Even so, there is a lack of research on the impact it would have when working alongside one another. Furthermore, there is limited information on long-term outcomes of the therapies, both individually and combined. Future studies should focus on the integration of music therapy and CBI, addressing the impact it would have on not only ASD, but also for other types of disorders. Despite the few limitations mentioned, music therapy and CBI combined show significant promises for notable outcomes for children with ASD but would need further research conducted

for direct answers. Advancing this aspect can bring forward an alternative support alongside the current scarcity of therapies specifically tailored for ASD.

Methods Section

To effectively address my research question, a mixed methods approach was used to explore the effectiveness of MT and CBI through survey data. Data was collected from two different perspectives in two surveys: one for parents of children diagnosed with autism and another for music therapists who have worked with such children, both qualitatively and quantitatively. By broadening the target audience, this method aimed to increase credibility while introducing different experiences and perspectives.

Participants

There are two surveys: one concentrated specifically towards the parents of children diagnosed with autism and the other focused on music therapists who have had children patients diagnosed with autism.

The survey targeted to parents includes an assorted amount of questions qualitatively and quantitatively to collect measurable data while being able to gather firsthand observations (refer to Appendix A-1). While doing so, it incorporates optional open-ended questions to encourage participants to share personal experiences and provide detailed responses, which would allow for further insights and in-depth analysis of individual perspectives. Additionally, the majority of questions are tailored to exploring their emotional regulation and social interaction with others, while showing conditions and potential factors contributing to their experiences and answers. This design aims to capture both broad trends and insightful personal responses, offering a deeper understanding on this matter.

On the other hand, the survey directed towards music therapists was used to get professional perspectives while gaining a deeper understanding of how they work with children (refer to Appendix A-2). While all participants shared a common background, they represented a variety of approaches to working with autistic children and levels of experience, allowing many angles from different from the same field.

Justifications

To justify the survey and methodology, the target audience was children (up to age 18) diagnosed with autism. This is because parents of younger individuals would be able to give more reliable answers. In contrast, the target audience being parents of adults may not have as great of a recollection as what was experienced in the past and may not be as emotionally attached to the child, possibly leading to further unreliability within the results. As children grow older and gain independence, parents have less direct involvement than the past, leading to gaps in their understanding. This is elaborated by Ting and Weiss, who state how “parents’ ability to respond sensitively to their child and maintain their child’s persistence toward the task, is important in children’s emotional development” (2017, p.15). By prioritizing parents with children up to age eighteen, the survey aims to gather valuable insights into their child’s emotional regulation and social interaction. Additionally, incorporating questions that explore parents’ perspectives on the potential impact of MT and CBI allows for further opinions towards this possible approach. The decision to focus participants to only music therapists was made to make sure that all data collected would have the core principles of music therapy. This brings greater relevance to the research question and gap while being able to minimize inconsistency in therapeutic approaches or conflicting methodologies that are possibilities when choosing a broader sample size.

To effectively gather a wide range of perspectives for two different target audiences, this study incorporated a survey-based methodology. Surveys were selected for their ability to collect both quantitative and qualitative data efficiently, which allows for a more diverse participation, capturing insights from throughout the world. As Caitlin Conner utilizes the same method of parent-reported surveys, their study effectively gathered parental perspectives on the difficulties of emotional regulation in children with ASD (Connor et al., p.1). Similarly, this study explores how an integrated approach supports children with ASD through the perspectives of parents, offering insight on their child's emotional regulation and social development with their specified therapeutic approach. In addition to the survey, optional structured interviews were conducted. While this was not the fundamental method of collecting data, this alternative way of collecting data served to provide additional context and further in-depth understanding of the participant's daily experiences and strategies used.

Procedure

To conduct this research, two surveys were distributed: one to parents, and the other to music therapists, both involving children with autism. These surveys assessed the level of support needs and the methods used to assess their emotional regulation and social interaction. The evaluation was measured by standardized tools such as the Emotional Regulation Checklist (ERC), the Sensory Sensitivity Scale (SeSS), and the Social Responsiveness Scale (SRS-2) in order to get responses measured on a scale of 1-5 to ensure accuracy. By collecting responses from individuals whose children or patients have or have not participated in music therapy, results between MT + CBI usage, MT only, or other sorts of therapies were analyzed for potential changes in emotional regulation and social interaction. Given the existing gap in the integration of CBI within MT, responses from both surveys will help determine whether CBI

would be beneficial and why. While doing so, comparing the effectiveness of CBI to current literature can also prove whether or not this approach would be productive. These findings will then be compared to external factors related to children with ASD who have undergone music therapy.

Limitations

While this study aims to provide insights into the effectiveness of MT combined with CBI for emotional regulation and social interaction in autistic children, there are some limitations when data collecting. One main limitation would be how the therapeutic exposure varied across responses. Differences in how these therapies are presented, whether through aspects like session length, personal improvisation, or even the clinical setting towards the patients, therefore influencing individual outcomes. Additionally, this study relied solely on personal data from parents and therapists, which introduces the possibility of bias. Parents have the possibility of not observing the therapy session firsthand or may request for modification to fit their expectations, while therapists improvise their sessions to suit each individual client, subsequently bringing inconsistent progression per person. Despite these limitations, this research brings a better understanding into music therapy combined with cognitive behavioral interventions while being able to add to the existing discussions in the field and point directions for future research.

Results Section

The results of this study contain both quantitative and qualitative analyses, examining the effects of music therapy (MT), cognitive behavioral interventions (CBI), the combination of both and how it develops the emotional regulation and social interaction in children with ASD.

Data Analysis - Therapists' Responses

For the qualitative analysis of therapist responses, thematic analysis was used to identify common themes and patterns within the data. A total of 19 music therapists participated in the survey, contributing both qualitative and quantitative data that illustrate the effectiveness and challenges of these therapies. These themes were then analyzed for trends in the therapists' insights, with a focus on their strategies, and perceptions on this approach (refer to Appendix B-1). For example, one concurring theme identified from several responses coming from one of the questions (refer to Appendix B-2) would be "Hard to Apply Skills Outside of Therapy," which was expressed by several therapists noting one of the few challenges that were prominent regarding emotional regulation and social interaction. This is one of the few themes from that question that demonstrate a commonality of ideas amongst therapists while being able to underscore the difficulty in achieving constant improvement within a short period of time.

As for the quantitative data, CBI usage by therapists was analyzed and categorized into two different groups. Results were then determined by averaging scores from two questions related to emotional regulation (refer to Appendix B-3) and two questions on social interaction (refer to Appendix B-4). This approach provided a clearer notion through a direct numerical comparison on how CBI positively impacted both aspects. This is particularly relevant to the underlying gap in existing research, as it emphasizes the need to explore alternative approaches while understanding the effects and implications of this perspective, which are both areas that have limited findings prior to this.

Data Analysis - Parents' Responses

From an alternative perspective, the quantitative data collected from twelve parents of children with ASD was derived from four key questions on emotional regulation (refer to

Appendix B-5) and five questions based on social interaction (refer to Appendix B-6). To analyze the data, I incorporated descriptive statistics to calculate averages on the emotional regulation and social interaction scores across all participants. These averages were then compared between the groups to identify any patterns, improvements, imbalances, and differences from the reported findings.

For the qualitative analysis, thematic analysis was utilized to explore children's emotional regulation and social interaction in their daily lives, as well as the positive and negative impacts of MT alongside CBI in the future. This qualitative component captured parents' experiences and perceptions to this hypothetical implementation, while being able to find repeating themes and further insights.

Findings

Therapist Findings

Analysis through descriptive statistics identified notable challenges in applying therapeutic skills outside structured clinical environments. Responses from nineteen music therapists were quantitatively analyzed and were systematically divided into two different groups based on their incorporation of CBI with MT. One group embodied therapists who actively used the combination of MT and CBI techniques and structures, while the other consisted of those utilizing MT without any supplementary methods supporting it. Numerical ratings based on a five-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 (no improvement) to 5 (significant improvement)) were averaged from two targeted survey questions related to emotional regulation (refer to Appendix B-3) and social interaction (refer to Appendix B-4).

Figure 1

CBI Incorporated MT Therapists: Ratings on Emotional Regulation and Social Interaction

Figure 1 illustrates individual ratings from therapists who incorporated a CBI-approach into music therapy. These questions are related to emotional regulation and social interaction and its effectiveness in their daily lives. Generally, all scores remain consistently high across all sections, particularly in structured effectiveness (Q7) and social queues (Q8), both of different aspects. While most therapists rated these topics between 3-5, there were also few anomalies, which may suggest individual factors that may have led to that specific response. The raw data corresponding to **Figure 1** can be found in Appendix C-1.

Figure 2

Non-CBI Incorporated Music Therapists: Ratings on Emotional Regulation and Social Interaction

On the other hand, **Figure 2** shows the ratings of therapists who did not incorporate CBI into their practice of music therapy. In comparison to **Figure 1**, these responses appear to be more varied and generally lower. In particular, this graph shows zero five-point ratings on the likert-scale and generally lower ratings in all four aspects, therefore highlighting the potential benefits and greater therapeutic outcomes associated with a CBI approach. The raw data for Non-CBI music therapists can be found on Appendix C-1.

Table 1

Comparison between CBI and Non-CBI usage in Music Therapy

Question	CBI Avg Response	Non-CBI Avg Response
Q6 - Struggle Regulating (ER)	3.2	3
Q7 - Structured Effectiveness (ER)	3.6	2.8
Q8 - Social Queues (SI)	3.1	3
Q9 - Social Training (SI)	3.1	2.2

The results averaged when comparing MT + CBI therapists to MT only therapists are shown in **Table 1**, which presents each group's views on the effectiveness of their practice and its importance to different real-life scenarios for both ER or SI. As individually depicted from **Figures 1** and **2**, therapists integrating CBI consistently reported high average scores across all surveyed questions.

As shown above, the greatest improvement was found in the area of structured effectiveness (refer to Appendix B-3, Q2) in correlation to emotional regulation, with a score of 3.6 compared to a score of 2.8 averaged by those using MT alone, indicating a moderate to substantial difference. These averages were based on individual responses (refer to Appendix C-1). Similarly, for social training effectiveness in correlation to social interaction (refer to Appendix B-4 Q2), it presents the largest difference in improvements, amounting to a 0.9-unit gap. This difference, nearing a full-point interval, highlights a significant difference in effectiveness between the two aspects. Smaller differences were also shown, with emotional regulation (refer to Appendix B-3, Q1) and understanding social cues (refer to Appendix B-4, Q1) with averages of 3.2 vs 3.0 and 3.1 vs 3.0 respectively. Overall, these results generally

indicate greater long-term progress, directly addressing my research gap on long-term effects of combined therapeutic approaches.

While **Table 1** highlights the overall difference in average scores between CBI and non-CBI therapists, **Figure 1** below breaks this down by individual therapist.

The qualitative responses from therapists revealed several themes related to challenges in therapy incorporation, such as difficulties, individual client preferences, precautions, and more while depending on the question (refer to Appendix B-1). An alternative perspective shows how the therapists also express concerns regarding barriers if MT and CBI were to be implemented, highlighting a lack of specialized training, support, and resources. Following these insights from therapists, quantitative findings from parents provided additional perspectives on the effectiveness of MT and CBI.

Parents' Findings

Figure 3

Parents' of Children who have undergone CBI + MT: Regards on Emotional Regulation and its Impact on their Child's Daily Life

Figure 3 addresses several factors within Emotional Regulation and to what extent they react to that specific scenario. Overall, “the section of calming down after upsetness” (refer to Appendix B-5, Q4) was the highest rated, suggesting that CBI and MT positively benefited this section the most, whereas another section like “unexpected changes in routine” (refer to Appendix B-5, Q2) received slightly lower average scores. Despite the differences, all sections on the graph have scored a likert-point of three or above, which suggests a general improvement across all emotional regulation aspects. Raw data can be found on Appendix C-2.

Figure 4

Parents of Children who have undergone MT + CBI: Regards on Social Interaction and its Impact on the Child's Daily Life

As shown above, **Figure 4** displays the responses of parents and how well their child reacts to five different situations (refer to appendix B-6) within the aspect of social interaction. From the graph, “group activities” shows the highest improvements of the five topics, averaging just below the maximum on the Likert scale. All of the other groups average a minimum of three and four, still reflecting positive impacts when incorporating CBI and MT. Raw data is located at Appendix C-3.

Figure 5

Parents of Children who have undergone Music Therapy: Regards on Emotional Regulation and its Impact on the Child’s Daily Life

Figure 5 displays the responses of parents on their child’s abilities to regulate their emotions. In contrast to **Figure 3**, which has significantly high scores, the scores of patients in **Figure 5** who have undergone MT only show scores of very minimal improvement, differing in groups between all participants. While some areas like “calming down after upsetness” and “use of self-soothing behaviors” (refer to Appendix B-5) show moderate improvement, there are other areas like “unexpected changes in routine” that show minimal improvement. This graph suggests that music therapy alone may offer limited benefits in supporting emotional regulation, in comparison to other therapies that may prove to be more viable. Raw data can be found on Appendix C-2.

Figure 6

Parents of Children who have undergone Music Therapy: Extent of Effectiveness towards Social Growth and Interaction in their Child's Daily Life

Figure 6 presents parents' thoughts on how effectively MT has been towards their child's overall social development. While some categories like "the ability to initiate conversation" or "sensitivity to noises" (refer to Appendix B-6) have had improvement, participants have also marked other areas like maintaining eye contact or social cues considerably low. This was also severely affected by one participant who rated many areas a minimal score, therefore lowering the overall averages. Due to low average scores as shown from the majority of participants, music therapy may prove to have an inconsistent or minimal impact on certain aspects of social growth. Raw data can be found at Appendix C-3.

Figure 7

Parents of Children who have undergone other Therapies: To what extent has it affected their emotional regulation in their Daily Lives?

When comparing **Figure 7** to other figures, it is shown how the majority of participants have received other forms of therapies beyond music therapy or CBI. Across all categories, results appear inconsistent, with some areas resulting in significant improvements contrasting others with little or moderate improvement. When depicting the graph, “unexpected changes in routine” and “calming down after upsetness” (refer to appendix B-5) have had the largest improvement, whereas sections like emotional outbursts have had a less notable score. This indicates more specific challenges that may need to be addressed, as alternative therapies prove to be less effective in some domains. Raw data can be found at Appendix C-2.

Figure 8

Parents with Children who have undergone other Therapies: To what Extent has it Affected their Social Interaction with Others?

Figure 8 represents the parents' thoughts on how other therapies have affected their social development with others. Across the five domains, responses show moderate levels of improvement, with some areas having higher scoring than others. For example, "group activities" and "initiate conversation" (refer to Appendix B-6) has shown slightly higher averages than sections like "sensitivity to noises," which were rated lower. This data in comparison to the effectiveness of other therapies to emotional regulation has shown similar results, as both display a moderate to high improvement. Raw data can be found at Appendix C-3.

Quantitative findings bring forward a complementary perspective in support of the therapists' data, which also illustrate a positive effectiveness of MT with CBI when developing the aspects of emotional regulation and social interaction. The parents' responses were categorized into three groups based on the type of therapy their child received: MT + CBI, MT only, and other types of therapies. Scores from multiple survey questions addressing emotional regulation and social interaction, which can be found on **Figures 3-8** (refer to Appendix B-5 and B-6), were averaged from these groups.

Table 2

The extent of different Therapies to Emotional Regulation and Social Interaction

Results	Emotional Regulation	Social Interaction
CBI + MT	3.75	3.20
MT Only	3.42	2.80
Other	3.04	2.97

Table 2 displays an analysis on ER and SI through individual parent responses. This data gives the average scores across key questions derived from raw data, separated by the type of therapy used (refer to Appendix C-3.)

The results of CBI + MT display the highest scores across both ER and SI. That said, other types of therapies have also proven results, even excelling in some sections compared to music therapy, which indicates its personal importance. Nevertheless, a more noticeable positive

trend was shown when MT was incorporated with a structured approach, which suggests the amount of possible benefits there when provided for children's development. Specifically, the MT + CBI group showed the highest mean scores, with an average of 3.75 for ER and 3.2 for SI, compared to the MT-only group (3.42 and 2.8, respectively) and the group receiving other therapies (3.04 and 2.97, respectively). These findings demonstrate how CBI + MT may offer better benefits for ER and SI, compared to utilizing music therapy or other therapies independently.

Discussion

This research addresses current gaps in the field of therapy, specifically towards the lack of structured and productive methods that explore how MT “may vary based on different treatment methods” (Zhao et al., 2025, p.16). Although past findings have shown benefits, Applewhite et al. (2022) states the lack of positive findings due to inconsistent methodologies and approaches. Both therapists and parents revealed clear advantages of this integrated approach. Quantitative findings demonstrated consistently higher scores from both groups when compared to any other type of therapy. In correlation to my gap, this study begins to address the lack of rigorous, high quality, and long-term research through a combined use of MT and CBI for children with ASD. While the research is not longitudinal in nature, it contributes valuable insights from alternative perspectives of both parents and therapists, many with over a decade of experience. Their Insights and reflections support the overall argument of this integration and the potential it has to improve ER and SI in children.

Limitations

One prominent limitation of this research would be the real-world barriers that affect both therapists and parents. Despite promising quantitative results, therapists spoke on constraints like

lack of resources, support, training & prior knowledge, and the overall barriers depending on the client. This was mentioned by therapist #1 and #3 (refer to Appendix B-1), stating how there would be a “[l]ack of trained practitioners” and the “[l]evel of support. I could incorporate this for the client with low support needs, but not for the ones with high support needs,” respectively. Alternatively, parents also show barriers solely through real-world limitations like costs, availability, and the overall specific needs of the child, as stated previously. For instance, parent #1 (refer to Appendix B-6) states how “[c]ost and availability were concerns. I prioritized therapies that helped him communicate and regulate emotions.” Rather than being able to explore a wide range of therapies, many parents are limited to the options that are most accessible and immediately beneficial. These constraints can lead to missed opportunities and even potential backlash, as the most “beneficial” or “popular” are not viable or effective for every person.

Given the amount of variability there is within the autism spectrum, individual differences in sensory sensitivities, emotional processing, and cognitive abilities play a big role on how each individual reacts to different experiences. As therapist #1 stated during an interview “to take into account people's sensory sensitivities, distinctive needs . . . and bring that into their understanding of their own emotional regulation and identification and meet those needs before you can do any higher level things,” it indicates the importance individualized care and how the mindset of “one-size-fits-all” is ineffective, as each child has unique challenges and needs. (refer to Appendix B-8)

Lastly, the small sample size poses a limitation to the study’s generalizability. While the data and overall findings provided context, the limited number of participants restrains the ideas

and thoughts of many others. Expanding the sample in future research would enhance the reliability of the results and allow for a deeper understanding of diverse experiences.

Future Directions

To build upon the findings of this study while further answering this current gap to a greater extent, future research should prioritize sustaining the integration of MT and CBI. As my research only addresses long-term information from the experiences of others instead of by nature, longitudinal research could determine whether initial improvements are maintained over time under varying conditions. Expanding to a greater diverse sample size would bring more credibility in research and provide a broader range of experiences and perspectives. This would allow for deeper research of how compatible and adaptable CBI and MT are across diverse individuals, as well as how the differences in each individual may influence outcomes. Another direction in which researchers can explore would be the components that are most effective with MT and CBI. From the two that are currently being researched, emotional regulation and social interaction, these aspects may not be the most compatible with MT and CBI where other approaches like sensory functioning and anxiety management may be more effective alongside MT and CBI.

Conclusion

This study explored the integration of music therapy (MT) and cognitive behavioral interventions (CBI) as a potential approach to improve emotional regulation (ER) and social interaction (SI) in children with autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Through qualitative and quantitative data from therapists and parents, this research demonstrated an overall positive impact in the effectiveness of combining these two interventions. While individual use of MT

and CBI were shown from previous studies, this research begins to fill a gap through an effective approach from an alternative intervention.

Despite limitations such as small sample size and barriers of implementation, results suggest that this integrated approach may offer a more comprehensive support for children compared to other interventions, specifically for ER and SI. Perspectives from experienced professionals and caregivers provide context to the overall findings, reinforcing the credibility of this method and how it would impact each child. Ultimately, this study contributes to a growing body of work, advocating for further long-term research. It lays important groundwork for future research to explore this integration through broader populations, longer durations of study, and more innovative interventions. With further investigation and refinement, the combined use of MT and CBI has the potential to become a more widely accepted and accessible intervention for supporting the emotional regulation and social growth of children with ASD.

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Appendix A - Survey Questions

A-1: Survey Questions - Parent of a Child diagnosed with ASD

Section 1 of 7 (Consent Form)

Section 2 of 7

Background Information

What is your child's age?

- Under 3
- 3-5
- 6-10
- 11-15
- 16-18
- 18+

How would you describe your child's level of support needs?

- Level 1 (Mild ASD) -- Requires some support but can function independently in structured settings.
- Level 2 (Moderate ASD) -- Requires significant support, struggles with communication and daily activities.
- Level 3 (Severe ASD) -- Requires very substantial support, has major difficulties in communication, emotional regulation, and independence.

What type of therapies has your child participated in? Select all that apply.

- Speech Therapy
- Music Therapy
- Behavioral Therapy (ABA, CBT, etc.)
- Physical Therapy
- Social Skills Training
- Cognitive Behavioral Interventions
- N/A
- Other...

Have you heard of music therapy or cognitive-behavioral interventions (CBI) as therapy options?

- Yes
- No

- Maybe

If so, feel free to share your experiences from music therapy or cognitive behavioral interventions (CBI).

Section 3 of 7

Emotional Regulation - Correlations

The measurement of emotional regulation is based on the Emotional Regulation Checklist (ERC), scaling from 1-5 (1 = Never, 5 = Always)

How often does your child experience emotional outbursts (meltdowns, aggression, crying, etc?)

- 1 - Never -- My child does not experience emotional outbursts.
- 2 - Rarely -- Happens but very infrequently.
- 3 - Sometimes -- My child experiences emotional outbursts occasionally.
- 4 - Often -- My child frequently has frequent outbursts.
- 5 - Always -- My child experiences very frequent outbursts, which happens in most situations.

How well does your child adjust to unexpected changes in routine?

- 1 - Not at all -- Completely resistant, major distress.
- 2 - Rarely -- Struggles significantly, needs full support.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Can adapt with preparation and moderate help.
- 4 - Often -- Can manage small changes with minor difficulty.
- 5 - Very well -- Easily adapts to routine changes.

Does your child use self-soothing behaviors (rocking, humming, hand-actions, etc) when distressed?

- 1 - Never -- My child does not use self-soothing behaviors when distressed.
- 2 - Rarely -- My child occasionally uses self-soothing behaviors, but it is uncommon.
- 3 - Sometimes -- My child engages in self-soothing behaviors in some situations but not always.
- 4 - Often -- My child frequently uses self-soothing behaviors when distressed.
- 5 - Always -- My child consistently engages in self-soothing behaviors as a primary coping mechanism.

How easily does your child calm down after becoming upset?

- 1 - Never -- Needs full intervention to calm down.

- 2 - Rarely -- Takes a long time to calm down, even with help.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Can self-regulate occasionally but often needs support.
- 4 - Often -- Calms down quickly with minimal support.
- 5 - Always -- Can independently calm down without help.

How sensitive is your child to loud noises, bright lights, or unexpected physical touch?

This question goes based off of a Sensory Sensitivity Scale (SeSS), scaling from 1 = Not sensitive, 5 = Extremely sensitive.

- 1 - Not Sensitive -- My child has little to no reaction.
- 2 - Mildly Sensitive -- My child is not significantly bothered.
- 3 - Moderately Sensitive -- My child sometimes struggles but can tolerate it with support.
- 4 - Sensitive -- My child frequently reacts negatively and may avoid certain environments.
- 5 - Extremely Sensitive -- My child has strong, immediate reactions.

Can you describe a situation where your child struggled with emotional regulation and what strategies helped?

Beyond the previous example, are there other common situations where your child struggled with emotional regulation? What strategies have worked best? (optional)

Section 4 of 7

Social Interaction - What Correlations are Shown?

In this section, the measurement of social interaction is based off of the Social Responsiveness Scale (SRS-2) where it is scaled through numbers 1-5. 1 = Never, 5 = Always

How often does your child initiate conversations with peers or adults?

- 1 - Never -- My child does not calm down without external intervention.
- 2 - Rarely -- My child struggles significantly.
- 3 - Sometimes -- My child occasionally calms down on their own.
- 4 - Often -- My child calms down quickly with minimal support.
- 5 - Always -- My child constantly self-regulates and calms down without assistance.

Does your child maintain eye contact during social interactions?

- 1 - Never -- Avoids eye contact entirely.
- 2 - Rarely -- Brief eye contact but mostly avoids it.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Can maintain eye contact in certain situations.
- 4 - Often -- Looks at others when talking but not always.
- 5 - Always -- Naturally maintains eye contact in conversations.

How well does your child understand social cues (facial expressions, tone of voice, etc)?

- 1 - Never -- Does not recognize social cues.
- 2 - Rarely -- Notices some but misinterprets them.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Understands some cues but struggles often.
- 4 - Often -- Interprets most cues correctly.
- 5 - Always -- Easily understands social cues in conversations.

How comfortable is your child in group activities?

- 1 - Never -- Avoids or refuses group activities.
- 2 - Rarely -- Struggles and needs encouragement.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Participates but with some discomfort.
- 4 - Often -- Joins in and engages fairly well.
- 5 - Always -- Enjoys and actively participates in group activities.

What are the biggest challenges your child faces in social interactions?

Are there any other challenges or experiences that you would like to share? (Optional)

Section 5 of 7

Correlation to Music Therapy and CBI

Music therapy utilizes music as a tool to achieve various goals, such as reducing stress, enhancing quality of life, and promoting overall well-being. Cognitive Behavioral Intervention (CBI) is a structured approach that empowers individuals to gain a deeper understanding of their own behavior. Through CBI, individuals learn to analyze their thoughts, identify patterns of increasing negativity, and apply effective strategies to modify those thoughts and emotions in a constructive way.

Has your child ever participated in music therapy?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what are your thoughts or observations about its effectiveness?

If your child has participated in music therapy, was it structured with specific cognitive behavioral techniques (CBI-based music therapy)?

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure

If yes, how did their emotional regulation and social interaction change after starting CBI-based music therapy?

- Improved significantly
- Improved somewhat
- No change
- Worsened somewhat
- Worsened significantly

If your child has not participated in music therapy, what are the reasons?

Have you heard of CBI (Cognitive Behavioral Intervention) in relation to music therapy?

- Yes
- No

Would you be open to trying a structured CBI-based music therapy program for your child?

- Yes, I would be interested
- Maybe, I would need more information
- No, I don't think it would be beneficial

What concerns or barriers might you have regarding CBI-based music therapy?

Section 6 of 7

General Feedback

What factors did you consider when choosing therapy options for your child with autism? What advice would you give to other parents making this decision?

Is there anything else you'd like to share about your experiences with therapy, such as challenges, benefits, or unexpected outcomes?

How do you think music therapy and CBI have (or could have) impacted your child's development and well-being?

Section 7 of 7

Thank you for your time!

Thank you for your consideration and time you spent on answering my survey and please feel free to email me about any questions that you may have on this matter at

[REDACTED] Thanks!

A-2: Survey Questions - Therapists with Patients Diagnosed with ASD

Section 1 of 7

Section 2 of 7

About Yourself! - Background and Professional Experience

What type of therapist are you?

- Music Therapist
- Occupational Therapist
- Occupational Therapy
- Behavioral Therapist
- Other...

Section 3 of 7

ASD Severity and Classification

What percentage of your ASD patients would you classify under the following categories (Mild, Moderate, Severe)?

- | | | | | |
|------------|--------|--------|--------|---------|
| ● 0-20% | 21-40% | 41-60% | 61-80% | 81-100% |
| ● Mild | | | | |
| ● Moderate | | | | |
| ● Severe | | | | |

Which of the following aspects of ASD do your patients struggle with the most? Check all that apply.

- Emotional regulation (meltdowns, difficulty calming down)
- Social interaction (initiating conversation, understanding social cues)
- Sensory processing (overstimulation, sensory-seeking behaviors)
- Communication difficulties

Which tools or reports do you rely on when determining the severity of ASD in patients? (Check all that apply)

- Reports from psychologists or developmental specialists
- ADOS-2 (Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule)
- Parent/caregiver interviews
- Clinical Observation
- Other...

Section 4 of 7

Emotional Regulation and Social Interaction

In this section, the measurement of emotional regulation is based on the Emotional Regulation Checklist (ERC) Scale, scaling from 1-5 (1 = Never, 5 = Always). The measurement of social interaction is based off of the Social Responsiveness Scale (SRS-2) where it is scaled through numbers 1-5. 1 = Never, 5 = Always.

How often do your ASD patients struggle to regulate emotions in therapy sessions?

- 1 - Never -- No difficulties regulating emotions.
- 2 - Rarely -- Minor struggles, occasional interventions needed.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Noticeable difficulties but manageable with support.
- 4 - Often -- Frequent challenges, requiring structured intervention.
- 5 - Always -- Severe and persistent emotional regulation struggles.

How well do ASD patients respond to structured interventions for emotional regulation?

- 1 - Not effective -- No noticeable improvement.
- 2 - Slightly effective -- Some minor improvements over time.
- 3 - Moderately effective -- Helps in some situations but not all.
- 4 - Effective -- Produces consistent improvements.
- 5 - Very effective -- Strong and consistent improvement in regulation.

How frequently do ASD patients struggle to interpret social cues?

- 1 - Never -- Understands social cues without difficulty.
- 2 - Rarely -- Occasional struggles but generally understands.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Some difficulty but improves with guidance.
- 4 - Often -- Regularly struggles to interpret cues.
- 5 - Always -- Severe and constant difficulty with social cues.

How effective are social training activities in improving ASD patients' interactions?

- 1 - Not effective -- No noticeable changes.
- 2 - Slightly effective -- Some small improvements.
- 3 - Moderately effective -- Helps in some social situations.
- 4 - Effective -- Leads to clear improvements in social interaction.
- 5 - Very effective -- Strong positive impact on social engagement.

What are the biggest challenges you face when working with ASD patients regarding emotional regulation and social interaction?

Section 5 of 7

Music Therapy and Cognitive Behavioral Interventions (CBI)

Music therapy utilizes music as a tool to achieve various goals, such as reducing stress, enhancing quality of life, and promoting overall well-being. Cognitive Behavioral Intervention (CBI) is a structured approach that empowers individuals to gain a deeper understanding of their own behavior. Through CBI, individuals learn to analyze their thoughts, identify patterns of increasing negativity, and apply effective strategies to modify those thoughts and emotions in a constructive way.

Have you ever used music therapy as part of treatment for ASD patients?

- Yes
- No

If yes, what improvements did you observe?

- Increased engagement
- Reduced Anxiety
- Improved Social Skills
- No effect
- Other...

Have you ever incorporated CBI techniques into music therapy sessions?

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure

If yes, did you observe differences in emotional regulation or social interaction before and after CBI-based music therapy?

- 1 - No improvement -- No changes observed.
- 2 - Slight improvement -- Some minor positive changes.
- 3 - Moderate improvement -- Noticeable benefits in certain situations.
- 4 - Significant improvement -- Clear and consistent benefits.
- 5 - Very strong improvement -- Highly effective in improving emotional regulation and social interaction.

Are you familiar with CBI-based music therapy?

- Yes
- No

Would you be interested in integrating CBI into therapy sessions if research supported its effectiveness?

- Yes
- Maybe, but I would need more information.

- No, it wouldn't fit my practice.

What barriers do you see in implementing music therapy or CBI for ASD patients?

Do you have any additional thoughts or insights on the use of Cognitive Behavioral Interventions (CBI) and Music Therapy for ASD patients?

Section 6 of 7

General Opinion and Insights

In your opinion, how do you think music could support therapeutic interventions for children? How do you engage with music personally or professionally, and do you see any therapeutic potential in it?

What advice would you give for developing interventions that combine music therapy with behavioral approaches?

Is there anything else you'd like to share about your experience with music, behavioral interventions, or your therapy sessions with your patients?

Section 7 of 7

Thank you for your Time!

Thank you for participating in this survey. Please feel free to email me any questions that you may have at [REDACTED]. Thanks!

**Appendix B - Qualitative and Quantitative Responses used for Data Analysis,
Findings, and Discussion**

B-1: Thematic Analysis on the Qualitative Data from Music Therapists

Hard to Apply Skills Outside of Therapy

Individual Differences Among Clients

Compliance and Behavior

Societal Pressure

Regulation through Foundational Skills

What are the biggest challenges you face when working with ASD patients regarding emotional regulation and social interaction?

Responses:

Not enough time to practice skills (1-2 hrs clinical time per patient per week). And caregivers are busy juggling other therapist and school and life. Hard for them to take time to always practice skills at home they're just trying to get by day to day.

Neuronormative expectations of what is considered "normal", "typical" or "appropriate" social interactions without regard for what the actual behaviour being presented is actually communicating.

Finding what music is soothing that particular day. Preferences change.

The biggest challenges are the barriers they face. Not their behavior, communication style, or emotions. But how their environment and society at whole decides to not accommodate them in any way, and discriminate against them.

Sensory regulation and body awareness prerequisite for emotional regulation and social interaction

I wouldn't use the term challenge. Each person has their unique way of expressing themselves. Once you learn how to communicate with them in their way, most challenges evaporate.

For emotional regulation, translation of skills outside of session

In a group setting, tools to assist in regulation are different for everyone so what is calming for one child may not work for another one.

My biggest struggles as a clinician who works and worked with ASD patients is providing structure which still allows them explore themselves and their own ways of self expression.

Structure provides a great outline, but sometimes also relies on compliance, which can further escalate emotional dysregulation

Balancing the true needs of the client with what society, school or caregivers are expecting of them (forcing eye contact, forced restriction of stimming, etc. are more harmful than they are warranted for clients with autism to exist in the world socially). Stimming is a big one for the paradox between emotional regulation and social interaction- social norms say the repetitive stimming/flapping should be reduced, yet this is the best way for my client to self-regulate!

One clients big feeling causing a 'domino effect' to their peers around them.

Generalization from individual to group settings is the biggest challenge.

Assessing how they learn best and what interventions will be best when considering generalization across settings

Identifying emotions, regulating through them

School based regulations

"Emotional regulation - managing changes in schedule, lack of access to preferred items, being flexible

Social interaction - initiating conversation, staying on topic"

Willingness to participate, then generalizing to use outside of therapy

Risk of physical harm to myself and to the client. Most of my clients SIB when their needs aren't met right away

Hard to Apply Skills Outside of Therapy	4	18%
Individual Differences	5	23%
Compliance and Behavior	3	14%
Societal Pressure	5	23%
Regulation via Foundational Skills	5	23%

Themes:

Lack of Training or Knowledge

Lack of Resources and Support

Discrimination and Societal Barriers

Barriers depending on Client

Prior Knowledge

2. "What barriers do you see in implementing music therapy or CBI for ASD patients?"

Lack of trained practitioners this is a very specialized field.

I have never heard of CBI. I know that Cognitive Behavioural Therapy techniques have been shown to be ineffective for Neurodivergent patients so I question the validity of something with a similar name, and therefore likely a similar premise

Level of support. I could incorporate this for the client with low support needs, but not for the ones with high support needs. There needs to be a certain level of receptive language and then expressive language (verbal, written, gestures, etc.) first.

The barriers are the discrimination that autistic people face daily from their caregivers, therapists, doctors, and all systems designed viewing them as the problem, rather than simply accommodating them.

I see most benefit from body-based experiential therapy in this setting. Using limited verbal processing and maximizing sensory regulation and active interaction with whatever topics we are addressing.

Lack of training on what specifically is unique to the approach

Behavioral techniques don't fit well into my theoretical orientation, and I find those techniques result in limited positive outcomes, when music is capable of so much more.

Cost, not trained in CBI

CBI often relies on the patient understanding the cause and effects of their emotions and in turn their behaviors. Patients with ASD cannot recognize that their emotions fuel their behaviors which are often socially "unacceptable" by our society's standards. Patients with ASD also often rely on patterns and expectations. If music is stopped/started to reinforce a behavior within a session, they may modify behavior there but not generalize that outside of music therapy for an extended period of time. I find CBI is helpful some, but not all of the time.

Barriers of CBI for autistic patients have seemed to deny the reality that discrimination is inherent in how the world views autism. (ie. modifying the client's own thoughts/feelings around the fact that others are discriminating/judging doesn't feel appropriate when this is their lived reality of how autism is seen as a disorder, versus the naturally occurring neurotype that it is).

Making the skill transferable

This is already the approach I use with those who have verbal skills and cognition to process the music based cognitive behavioral strategies. Some clients need less structured, play based approaches for emotional regulation through relational co-regulation due to being in a pre-verbal stage of development. A client cannot access CBI without functional communication and cognitive ability; therefore, it is not an intervention for all clients with ASD.

Barriers to implementing CBI could include the potential for focusing only on behavior and forgetting the origin of the need.

Is there a certification you need?

Lack of awareness of music therapy, lack of funding/financial barriers

Need more time each week to spend with my individuals. One hour per week is not enough to truly engrain the skills.

Depends on the level of functioning. Plus: we need to be mindful that as music therapists we are there to empower clients. It's not our job to make neurodivergent people fit into neurotypical boxes. I prefer social emotional learning over CBI

COMBINED THEMES WITH PRIOR QUESTION - Do you have any additional thoughts or insights on the use of Cognitive Behavioral Interventions (CBI) and Music Therapy for ASD patients?

CBI is typically most helpful with patients with more typical intellectual functioning. Intellectual disability can impair the effectiveness of these interventions and adaptations need to be found for the multitude of patients with ASD with severe intellectual or learning disabilities to make the ideas make sense to them. It also requires high caregiver support and involvement thus high caregiver training implying the caregivers have the time and mental bandwidth to learn and implement this new skill. This is unfortunately a small percentage of caregivers though in my experience they all try their best. It is just a very hard job being a caregiver and navigating the Medicaid/insurance/multiple therapies a week space. It's draining. It is all the more important for them to learn these skills for both themselves and to help their kids but it can be a slow road. I would have to see the first voice data from autistic voices on CBI before I make a decision on its use in my practice

See above. Communication to confirm understanding and appropriateness is a barrier.

Treating behavior is not effective. Autistic people's behavior is not the problem. The discrimination and dehumanization they face is the problem. As well as systems designed against them that are determined to make them fail, and punish them for it.

The language throughout this survey has been very pathologizing - severity, patient, intervention. Those within the ASD community are working hard to advocate for language and approaches that are affirming of difference, as opposed to seeking to correct or extinguish. I would encourage you to seek out this affirming and supportive research and work.

Neurodiversity Affirming practices should be taken into consideration when looking at shaping behavior.

Need more information on the topic first.

I am curious to learn more!

While it can be very effective for some, it is not the best for all clients with ASD.

Lack of training or knowledge	13	39%
Lack of Resources or Support	6	18%
Discrimination	4	12%
Barriers Depending on Client	10	30%

Themes

Effectiveness/Application of Music Therapy

Personal Experiences

Support to Clients

Integration with other therapies/approaches

In your opinion, how do you think music could support therapeutic interventions for children?

Makes examples more tangible. I use the Zones of Regulation curriculum. Music helps illustrate it more plainly.

Very well. It depends on the child, situation and type of intervention, as everyone is different, but generally speaking it's great. I am literally a music therapist, it is my job to support music interventions for children.

I have a Masters in Music Therapy. I provide an integrative child-led therapeutic approach.

Music Therapy is evidence based and effective when patient preferred.

Music is a trusted ally to children. Music uses both hemispheres of the brain to reach people in different ways than anything else. It can be a nonverbal medium for them to participate actively or passively.

Yes, when appropriately incorporated

There's not much attributed to opinion. There's a score of research that shows the benefit of music when working with children of a variety of diagnoses. Music has been used to help children communicate, increase cognitive skills, music relaxation techniques leads to increased emotional regulation. There's more than could be said in a short answer comment.

Yes, music therapists don't own music. But music can cause harm and should be used cautiously by non-MT-BCs

As an MT-BC, I find significant benefits to using music to support therapeutic interventions for children. I often co-treat with other therapies (OT/PT/SLP) and utilize music to motivate and supplement hard tasks for my patients

Music allows for wordless expression, less pressure to explore and create, freedom in accessing the inner self with little constraints of doing it "right". I see this as the major goal that will be the bedrock for any further skill development

Very effectively

Music is an organizing multi-sensory input that facilitates regulation of the nervous system. Supports cognition and memory when learning and practicing skills, encourages engagement with more preferred experiences

Music is a great tool that motivates a lot of kids. The elements of music can be changed to support emotional and physical needs

Integral practice approach, adjusting approaches based on client needs

Music is a fun, engaging, and often highly preferred activity for children. Music can make interventions more fun and engaging and help children regulate their emotions.

Music is a highly regarded motivator for a vast number of children. Music helps children learn, retain, and grow.

Effectiveness/Application of Music Therapy	15	45%
Personal Experiences	5	15%
Supporting Clients	9	27%
Different Approaches	4	12%

Themes

Effectiveness of Music Therapy to other Structural Approaches

Importance of Professional Training

Dependent on each Individual Client

Caution and Ethical Considerations

What advice would you give for developing interventions that combine music therapy with behavioral approaches?

Use music as either the motivation or the structure for the desired behavior.

Listen to first voices, and marginalized people who are experiencing the actual therapy. They can give the best insights into if the therapy is effective or not.

Continue learning and taking CMTEs on the matter.

Get rid of behavioral approaches. Focusing on the behavior does not get to the root. Punishing behavior is an unhealthy and ineffective way to attempt to help someone navigate their environment. I would also refrain from saying "ASD clients" as the vast majority of autistic people prefer the term "autistic person." It is not a disorder, it is a neurotype.

Consult music therapists. Be aware of behavioral responses to the music used, make changes when necessary. Not every song is appropriate for every person

There's a lot that goes behind it, and one would need to be educated in the practice at and pass a music therapy board exam. It's licensed in some states. If this is not an option, find a certified music therapist to collaborate with.

Be cautious about your intentions to avoid harm

I would give the advice that though music interventions can be highly structured, room needs to be given for deviations of behavior and exploration of unexpected emotions within improvisation. Prioritize the true needs of the client, not how society demands they exist.

Discuss with an MT-BC about any music-based interventions you are thinking about using.

Obtain training in music therapy from an approved music therapy college program.

Consider what skill is being taught and whether it is in line with the presentation of a child. Work together with other professionals, don't make assumptions and ask questions to the right, qualified people.

There is absolutely a time to stop a behavioral technique in favor of preserving the relationship in therapy, since working on behaviors fundamentally isolates elements of the client, which can be negative.

Consult an MT-BC, be aware that there is no specific type of music that is inherently "calming" or therapeutic. Be aware of client preferences.

Rely heavily on the predictability of musical structure.

To be mindful of possible implication or harm caused by behavioral approaches including but not limited to edible reinforcements, timers, and screen time.

Effectiveness/Application of Music Therapy	8	26%
Personal Experiences	8	26%
Supporting Clients	6	19%
Different Approaches	9	29%

B-2: Example of Recurring Theme from a Question - Therapist THEMATIC Analysis

Hard to Apply Skills Outside of Therapy

Individual Differences Among Clients

Compliance and Behavior

Societal Pressure

Regulation through Foundational Skills

What are the biggest challenges you face when working with ASD patients regarding emotional regulation and social interaction?

Responses:

Not enough time to practice skills (1-2 hrs clinical time per patient per week). And caregivers are busy juggling other therapist and school and life. Hard for them to take time to always practice skills at home they're just trying to get by day to day.

Neuronormative expectations of what is considered "normal", "typical" or "appropriate" social interactions without regard for what the actual behaviour being presented is actually communicating.

Finding what music is soothing that particular day. Preferences change.

The biggest challenges are the barriers they face. Not their behavior, communication style, or emotions. But how their environment and society at whole decides to not accommodate them in any way, and discriminate against them.

Sensory regulation and body awareness prerequisite for emotional regulation and social interaction

I wouldn't use the term challenge. Each person has their unique way of expressing themselves.

Once you learn how to communicate with them in their way, most challenges evaporate.

For emotional regulation, translation of skills outside of session

In a group setting, tools to assist in regulation are different for everyone so what is calming for one child may not work for another one.

My biggest struggles as a clinician who works and worked with ASD patients is providing structure which still allows them explore themselves and their own ways of self expression.

Structure provides a great outline, but sometimes also relies on compliance, which can further escalate emotional dysregulation

Balancing the true needs of the client with what society, school or caregivers are expecting of them (forcing eye contact, forced restriction of stimming, etc. are more harmful than they are warranted for clients with autism to exist in the world socially). Stimming is a big one for the paradox between emotional regulation and social interaction- social norms say the repetitive stimming/flapping should be reduced, yet this is the best way for my client to self-regulate!

One clients big feeling causing a 'domino effect' to their peers around them.

Generalization from individual to group settings is the biggest challenge.

Assessing how they learn best and what interventions will be best when considering generalization across settings

Identifying emotions, regulating through them

School based regulations

"Emotional regulation - managing changes in schedule, lack of access to preferred items, being flexible

Social interaction - initiating conversation, staying on topic"

Willingness to participate, then generalizing to use outside of therapy

Risk of physical harm to myself and to the client. Most of my clients SIB when their needs aren't met right away

Hard to Apply Skills Outside of Therapy	4	18%
Individual Differences	5	23%
Compliance and Behavior	3	14%
Societal Pressure	5	23%
Regulation via Foundational Skills	5	23%

B-3: Quantitative Emotional Regulation Questions for Analysis (Therapist)

Q1) How often do your ASD patients struggle to regulate emotions in therapy sessions?

- 1 - Never -- No difficulties regulating emotions.
- 2 - Rarely -- Minor struggles, occasional interventions needed.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Noticeable difficulties but manageable with support.
- 4 - Often -- Frequent challenges, requiring structured intervention.
- 5 - Always -- Severe and persistent emotional regulation struggles.

Q2) How well do ASD patients respond to structured interventions for emotional regulation?

- 1 - Not effective -- No noticeable improvement.
- 2 - Slightly effective -- Some minor improvements over time.
- 3 - Moderately effective -- Helps in some situations but not all.
- 4 - Effective -- Produces consistent improvements.
- 5 - Very effective -- Strong and consistent improvement in regulation.

B-4: Quantitative Social Interaction Questions for Analysis (Therapist)

Q1) How frequently do ASD patients struggle to interpret social cues?

- 1 - Never -- Understands social cues without difficulty.
- 2 - Rarely -- Occasional struggles but generally understands.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Some difficulty but improves with guidance.
- 4 - Often -- Regularly struggles to interpret cues.
- 5 - Always -- Severe and constant difficulty with social cues.

Q2) How effective are social training activities in improving ASD patients' interactions?

- 1 - Not effective -- No noticeable changes.
- 2 - Slightly effective -- Some small improvements.
- 3 - Moderately effective -- Helps in some social situations.
- 4 - Effective -- Leads to clear improvements in social interaction.
- 5 - Very effective -- Strong positive impact on social engagement.

B-5: Analysis of Quantitative Data from Parents on Emotional Regulation

How often does your child experience emotional outbursts (meltdowns, aggression, crying, etc?)

- 1 - Never -- My child does not experience emotional outbursts.
- 2 - Rarely -- Happens but very infrequently.
- 3 - Sometimes -- My child experiences emotional outbursts occasionally.
- 4 - Often -- My child frequently has frequent outbursts.
- 5 - Always -- My child experiences very frequent outbursts, which happens in most situations.

How well does your child adjust to unexpected changes in routine?

- 1 - Not at all -- Completely resistant, major distress.
- 2 - Rarely -- Struggles significantly, needs full support.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Can adapt with preparation and moderate help.
- 4 - Often -- Can manage small changes with minor difficulty.
- 5 - Very well -- Easily adapts to routine changes.

Does your child use self-soothing behaviors (rocking, humming, hand-actions, etc) when distressed?

- 1 - Never -- My child does not use self-soothing behaviors when distressed.
- 2 - Rarely -- My child occasionally uses self-soothing behaviors, but it is uncommon.
- 3 - Sometimes -- My child engages in self-soothing behaviors in some situations but not always.
- 4 - Often -- My child frequently uses self-soothing behaviors when distressed.
- 5 - Always -- My child consistently engages in self-soothing behaviors as a primary coping mechanism.

How easily does your child calm down after becoming upset?

- 1 - Never -- Needs full intervention to calm down.
- 2 - Rarely -- Takes a long time to calm down, even with help.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Can self-regulate occasionally but often needs support.
- 4 - Often -- Calms down quickly with minimal support.
- 5 - Always -- Can independently calm down without help.

B-6: Analysis of Quantitative Data from Parents on Social Interaction

How sensitive is your child to loud noises, bright lights, or unexpected physical touch?

This question goes based off of a Sensory Sensitivity Scale (SeSS), scaling from 1 = Not sensitive, 5 = Extremely sensitive.

- 1 - Not Sensitive -- My child has little to no reaction.
- 2 - Mildly Sensitive -- My child is not significantly bothered.
- 3 - Moderately Sensitive -- My child sometimes struggles but can tolerate it with support.
- 4 - Sensitive -- My child frequently reacts negatively and may avoid certain environments.
- 5 - Extremely Sensitive -- My child has strong, immediate reactions.

How often does your child initiate conversations with peers or adults?

- 1 - Never -- My child does not calm down without external intervention.
- 2 - Rarely -- My child struggles significantly.
- 3 - Sometimes -- My child occasionally calms down on their own.
- 4 - Often -- My child calms down quickly with minimal support.
- 5 - Always -- My child constantly self-regulates and calms down without assistance.

Does your child maintain eye contact during social interactions?

- 1 - Never -- Avoids eye contact entirely.
- 2 - Rarely -- Brief eye contact but mostly avoids it.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Can maintain eye contact in certain situations.
- 4 - Often -- Looks at others when talking but not always.
- 5 - Always -- Naturally maintains eye contact in conversations.

How well does your child understand social cues (facial expressions, tone of voice, etc)?

- 1 - Never -- Does not recognize social cues.
- 2 - Rarely -- Notices some but misinterprets them.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Understands some cues but struggles often.
- 4 - Often -- Interprets most cues correctly.
- 5 - Always -- Easily understands social cues in conversations.

How comfortable is your child in group activities?

- 1 - Never -- Avoids or refuses group activities.
- 2 - Rarely -- Struggles and needs encouragement.
- 3 - Sometimes -- Participates but with some discomfort.
- 4 - Often -- Joins in and engages fairly well.
- 5 - Always -- Enjoys and actively participates in group activities

B-7: Qualitative Responses from Parents on Emotional Regulation, Social Interaction, and Insights on CBI + MT

Themes

Noise Sensitivity and Tolerance

Effectiveness of CBI/MT

Interest in MT/Intervention Approaches

Mixed Therapy Approaches

Limited Success from Limitations

If so, feel free to share your experiences from music therapy or cognitive behavioral interventions (CBI).

In my experience music therapy is amazing; however, my son had noise sensitivity and struggled with noises. By high school he was able to be in band class but he could not tolerate noises as a young child.

CBI was attempted but it was not very successful; it was mostly because it was during COVID, and we had to do it virtually. My son was 7 at the time, and he did not have the emotional maturity or attention span.

Heard but never tried

Music therapy helped my son express emotions through rhythm. CBI taught him to recognize anxiety triggers. Together, they made a difference in self-awareness.

We've heard about music therapy but haven't tried it yet.

We've done ABA, but music therapy is something we're considering

Noise Sensitivity and Tolerance	1	10%
Effectiveness of CBI/MT	2	20%
Interest in MT/Intervention Approaches	2	20%
Mixed Therapy Approaches	2	20%
Limited Success from Limitations	3	30%

Themes

Costs & Availability

Specific Needs of the Child

Miscellaneous

What factors did you consider when choosing therapy options for your child with autism?
What advice would you give to other parents making this decision?

COMBINED WITH

What concerns or barriers might you have regarding CBI-based music therapy?

I like CBI but would worry about how noise sensitivity could be prohibitive.

Time

Cost and travel distance

Cost and availability were concerns. I prioritized therapies that helped him communicate and regulate emotions.

Access and understanding how it works

Finding trained therapists who work with high-needs children

N/a

Therapies should be based on the specific sensitivities of the child. Every ASD symptom is highly individualized and there is no one-size fits-all approach. There are also huge differences in the complexity of ASD and parents should be aware of the levels of peers in each therapy option.

Scheduling and the therapist's approach

What her needs are.

Cost and if my child shows any interest

I went to the centre with my aunt and the staff introduced me to the programs here

Cost and availability were big for us. We had to balance effectiveness with what we could realistically afford and access nearby. Advice: Don't feel guilty if you can't afford everything—progress can still happen with consistency.

I looked at how well the therapy matched my child's specific needs—like communication or sensory issues—rather than just what was most popular my issue right now is just finding places near by. Trust your instincts and choose what fits your child, not just what others recommend.

Anything engaging that doesn't overwhelm him is worth trying.

Cost and Availability	8	35%
Specific Needs of the Child	12	52%
Miscellaneous	3	13%

Themes

Would try Music Therapy and other Approaches Alongside

Impact of MT on Emotional Regulation

Impact of MT on Engagement and Expression

How do you think music therapy and CBI have (or could have) impacted your child's development and well-being?

As my son got older I think he could have tolerated music therapy; however, he will still often watch TV with captions with a super-low volume so I don't know if it would ever have been a real option.

I think it would have helped him regulate his emotions easier.

Not too sure. But willing to try if I knew more about it

Music and CBI together made it easier for him to understand and express emotions constructively

I think music could help with emotional expression and engagement, especially if paired with behavior strategies.

I think music might help him feel safe and less reactive if presented gently with behavioral support.

Would try Music Therapy and other Approaches Alongside	6	60%
Impact of MT on Emotional Regulation	2	20%
Impact of MT on Engagement and Expression	2	20%

B-8: Interview Transcription - Qualitative Data

I'm going to do a voice recording just because it'll be faster for me. So your first question, can you share an example of how music therapy has helped an autistic client with emotional regulation or social interaction? Any specific moments or patterns you've noticed?

Well, I use like I was talking about the zones of regulation system, or curriculum, which was created by some lady who's an occupational therapist. So

one, I think, in general, just being aware of one's own emotions, others emotions, and then the somatic cues of emotions. So like, for example, anxiety, those somatic cues might be racing heart or like

maybe sweaty palms, or you're moving around really fast, like pacing,

really rapid breathing, being aware of the somatic cues of each of your emotions, which is one of the things that the zones of regulation curriculum does really Well. Helps you to identify them better. Because a lot of times people with autism have,

I think it's called alexithymia, where it's like a really a disconnect from, like, their body and what the cues in their body means, like, it's hard to tell when they're hungry, or, like, when they have to go the bathroom, things like that. So doing some really intensive work on what does an

emotion feel like for you, because it's different for everybody, can be really helpful to recognizing the emotion. And then once you can consistently recognize the emotion, then it's

saying, is this emotion appropriate for the situation? Right now? You know, like you might be overjoyed and bouncing off the walls super loud, but if you're in a library, that's not necessarily a good fit. So then you can employ a coping skill that helps regulate your energy level, your

emotion level, something that might be calming, like Like Box breathing long exhales to try and slow down that nervous system, or listening to calming music, or certain rhythmic movements, like stretches that tend to be regulating things like that. So,

yeah, I mean, I definitely these are long, long term goals that you know can be lifelong goals.

And I think breaking it down into those smaller chunks is really helpful.

You also asked about social interactions? I mean, that's kind of a whole different category. So social interactions, I think a lot of times what my clients with autism struggle with is kind of

understanding all these unspoken rules and rituals, honestly, of social interactions. So using music to structure or memorize those is how I typically approach it. So whether it's, you

know, like

imitation is, or even just joint attention, excuse me, is like the first thing that you're looking to build with social interaction, especially like responding to joint attention that they do not

like initiate. So sorry, I'm trying to do two things at once. Okay, I'm here we go.

So, you know, music just sort of free music play is a great way to get that going, because music is often a really preferential fun activity. And you know, if you do something funny or cool or

interesting sounding a lot of times loud or fast is funny to kids,

then they'll want to imitate that, which is a great way to build those imitation skills. And, you know, trying to get them to buy into an activity that you present rather than, I mean, certainly

you have to respond to their bids for joint attention first to sort of build rapport, but then getting them to be interested in your bids for joint attention is really important too.

So you know, you have to kind of think about what that translates to in the real world. Yeah, you know, they could start an activity, but it's not always going to be that way. Like other kids will be like, Okay, we're playing this game. Like, do you want to join? You know, the world's not going to end up revolving around this child. So that's kind of a precursor step, and then once that interest in others is built and you have demonstrated to them that, hey, interacting with others is more engaging in some cases than your sort of internal world, which a lot of times, is incredibly engaging for people with autism. So you have to make a.

The music and the activity be that much more fun because with sensory differences and sort of the vivid

scripts that might be playing out in people, people's minds. You know, a lot of times you'll see scripting of like repeating phrases from like, Peppa Pig or something over and over, because they just really like that. You have to kind of cut through that mental static and be more interesting to show them like, hey,

life with others is fun. So once that's established, then you can start working on structures. So, you know, hello and goodbye is a great place to start making sure that they're waving or using their AAC device or verbally, you know, engaging at some point. And you know, hello songs are a great way to structure that um, giving opportunities, modeling first and then giving them opportunities to try whatever ways I use. There are many different ways to say hello. There are many different ways to say hello. You could wave with your hand, wave, wave, wave to say hello. You can wave your hand to say hello, wave, wave, um. And then you know, putting in you could use your voice to say hello.

You could use your voice to say and then they say hello, or that same thing. But with their AAC device, pressing the button Hello on their talker,

you can also do just like smiles or eye contact. I don't love to push eye contact because sometimes that's really uncomfortable for people with autism, so that's not one that I typically build into my Hello song. Okay, so then, you know, like taking turns is a important social skill, and music can structure that beautifully. You know, like it's your turn to play on a certain instrument that we're sharing for like, eight bars, and then it's my turn, and the structure of the music and the words reflect that. And maybe there's some sort of musical cue for, like, switching, you know, and then using the words your turn, my turn, or often I use, like, Mallory's turn, clients names turn, because it's a little bit more concrete than, like, the more abstract concept of your and mine, all right. And then

as they get farther and farther along in that, get good at, you know, turn taking, you know, building in manners, please and thank you. You can use more like, social story songs to show when it's important to say, and like, help them memorize when it's important to say please and thank you. And then, you know, maybe make a musical cue for those phrases. Like,

like, if there's a time that like, you're really hoping they'll say please, you might be like, What's the magic word? You know, just kind of having, like a special musical cue along with that, like verbal cue that, like clues them in, oh, this is when I should say, please. Okay, and then making a big deal too. Like, oh my gosh, that made me feel so happy. Thank you, you know. And giving them a big, big payoff, because, again, music as the motivator is a huge use of music.

That is one of the biggest things that I end up using with my clients, is like, when you do the desired behavior, you get a huge musical payoff, whether it's a favorite song or a funny sound or getting to play the instrument that you were wanting, whatever. Okay? And then, like, with more advanced clients, I have worked on the idea of threading. So, like, within a conversation, I might say, I went to Mexico last spring, so there's the threads that the next person could, or the person in the conversation with them, could pick out of that is Mexico, and then, like, travel in general and spring.

So then they can choose, like, one of those conversation topics to relate to.

Well, even pre this, you also want to be thinking about teaching the idea of comment or question. So like, you know, comments are obviously like, Oh, that's cool. Oh, interesting. And then a question would be

expanding. And then maybe, you know, under the comment, sort of sub heading would be like relating,

because that's then where you would use the threading, which is,

that's a tricky one. I've had limited success with this. I want to sort of use it.

More, but a lot of my clients so I can experiment and see what works best. But a lot of my clients are in the, you know, like responding to joint attention phase or just like imitating, you know, more the basic, basic social skills. But, you know, the idea is that you would meet use the music and the structure of the activity as a metaphor for this idea of threading. So

I wish I could send you a video with a client, but I'm driving right now, but you're playing an instrument, and you play maybe like really fast and so then they have to take some element of what you've just played and imitate it or expand on it. So, like, play really fast. And then, you know, their new idea is, play really slow. Now it's my turn, so I'm gonna imitate it and expand. So now I'm gonna play really slow, and then maybe, like, a certain rhythm pattern, and then maybe they take that and turn it into, like, Duh.

So there's an element of what I did, and then they're expanding on it. So the idea is like threading is weaving this,

you know, or just following this thread through the conversation of you know, this is connected to this is connected to this, and you have this more smooth and less disjointed, conversational style. So yeah, let me see what were your other questions.

Number two, are there any particular musical therapists techniques you found most effective for working with ASD patients? Well, I just talked about a lot, but yeah, as a broad idea, like the most the three most used techniques that I

employ in my practice would be music as motivator, music as structure. And so you can look into neurologic music therapy, especially, what's it called pattern

something I don't know. It's early in the book. It's about using the structure, like the rhythm, the ascending or descending nature of the melody, the like the texture, like how thick or sparse the sounds are, you know, many sounds versus one sound, the, you know, the meter, all these different things to structure the movement or the overall activity. And then the third would be music as metaphor, which I also use to illustrate those somatic experiences of emotions. So, you know, like we were talking about anxiety might be racing heartbeat, you know, really pacing around super fast, repetitive thoughts. So then I might play like, a really sort of like, or like, even just, like, the same pattern over and over and, like, really fast and maybe really loud too, because a lot of times, anxiety, sort of, like, is just the only thing that you can focus on, even if you're trying to do something else. And, you know, then I would like, calm feels like, you know, slow, soft, maybe, like a really thin texture, all these things.

But then again, music is functioning as the metaphor, as well as just kind of like making the somatic experiences more concrete and tangible so that they can relate. Oh, okay, I see.

All right, I'm pulling up to my destination, so I'm gonna stop here, but I'll check out number three and fill it out in a little bit. All right, okay,

back from dinner and going to address your third question, which is, what challenges have you encountered when implementing music therapy for autistic clients?

Think,

I mean, it's not so much a challenge as a consideration, and it takes some time to really fully kind of understand and to learn what each client's like, uniqueness is like, and how they sort of process the world, because

most clients with autism have significant sensor.

Differences, whether it's like the way they process like sensory information, or the sensory needs they have or sensory sensitivities they have. So like, for example, I have a client tonight with pretty severe

autism who like he

every time he got excited about like, he would move the chimes and it would make a noise, he'd get so excited that he had to, like, stand on his head, almost like he was on my couch in my studio, like, going full upside down. And so, you know, in the past, I wouldn't quite have known what to do and maybe ignored that, but now I'm able to say, Oh, wow, it seems like that really made you so excited that you needed pressure on your head. And so one of the things about emotional regulation is with clients with autism and many other conditions, you really have to

take into account how the sensory differences are a big part of their emotional regulation. So you know, rather than shying away from that or ignoring that, you lean into it and say, okay, cool. Well, you know, that's a great way to meet that need. But also, you know, there's not always going to be a soft couch, so let's see if we can teach you a way to get that pressure you're seeking by pushing down on your own head. So I would do hand over hand, and then try and get him to push on his head. It's like, I mean, I think the clinical term is, like, deep pressure, squeezes, or something like that. I don't remember the name, but that's what I call him. And so, you know, trying to teach him other alternative behaviors for when there's not, like a soft couch, because, you know, a hard floor isn't gonna be necessarily very safe to do that. And, you know, thinking long term, I would love a world that is accepting of all people's, you know, like neurological differences and diversity. But you know, if he's trying to mainstream long term, like, people are gonna look at him weird if he goes and tries to do a headstand all the time, but if he's kind of just like putting his hands on his head and pushing down, that's something that's a little more palatable for the general public. That's not my main concern, but my main concern is getting his needs met in a safe way. But you know, it's, it's things you have to think about when you're trying to think about long term mainstreaming for, you know, the good of the clients, like social acceptance and ability to form relationships. You know, there I didn't as a person. I really didn't know a lot about autism until I entered college, and so, you know, if I were to see somebody doing like, strange behaviors out in the world, I would have been like, whoa. You know, I've obviously learned a ton and grown a ton. But it's not the same for everybody that not, still, many people don't quite understand what Autism means. So

very long ramble to say that you really have to take into account people's sensory sensitivities, distinctive needs, whatever, and bring that into their understanding of their own emotional regulation and identification and meet those needs before you can do any higher level things, because it's often such a high again,

I'm going to refer to it as like static, almost that like you have to try and cut through and get those needs met before you can do higher level things, like maybe working on communication or academic cognitive goals, whatever intricate motor tasks that require a lot more concentration, things like that. The other thing is, oh, I had it.

Oh, different, yeah. So kind of in that vein, just like different ideas of what learning looks like. You know, if you grew up in a sort of neurotypical classroom, you might just be like, Okay, well, focus and learning look like sitting at your desk and paying attention. And, you know, I've again, had to really redefine what it means to under like how to teach and how to coach. And, you know, present material and assess if a client is understanding and think about their processing level and sort of their cognitive abilities. So, you know, giving way longer processing times presenting material in many, many different formats, whether it's auditory, then visual, then like tactile or kinesthetic. Obviously, in music therapy, we, you know, bring in like Sonic elements, like rhythm and pitch and everything, but presenting material for maybe lower functioning.

Cognitively level, cognitive level clients in many, many different ways, many, many times. And you know, taking those windows of even if they're like 32nd windows of opportunity, where you can see they're focused and they're listening, and finding a way to just jump in and get that material, that information to them, make it relevant and interesting to them in the moment. That's what I do love about music therapy, is you have to be on your feet, so engaged, so creative at all times, because it's just interesting. It makes it, you know, different. It's that's why I love this career path.

So, yeah, I would say those are the main things. And then your last was, if there's anything you'd like to share about your experience working with autistic clients, I'd love to hear your thoughts. I think I've covered most. I've rambled a lot, so I'm very sorry. This is all in audio format. I just am a person that I know.

I overwrite emails way too long, and I will take like, an hour on an email, and it's just I don't have that time in my schedule. So this is the way you're getting the information. I'm sorry if you needed to use a transcription software. Please do if you know any colleagues who work with autistic clients, I'd really appreciate it. I will. I have a couple people.

You know what I'll do? Because I there's many people. I'll just post it on our Facebook page. I'm in Colorado, so I'll post it on our music therapy Facebook page, and people can fill it out, and I'll tag the people that I know,

specifically that work with clients. So yeah, thank you so much, Ja[y]den, and good luck to you in your research. If you have any more questions, feel free to email back, or you can text me off, and that's leaving a little faster at

and I can give you more long, rambling audio answers. Have a good one. Bye, bye.

Appendix C - Statistics through Data Analysis

Appendix C-1: Therapists' Responses to Specific Situations

Please refer to Appendix B-3 and B-4 for full questions.

Therapist #	CBI Usage	Q6 - Struggle Regulating (ER)	Q7 - Structured Effectiveness (ER)	Q8 - Social Queues (SI)	Q9 - Social Training (SI)
Therapist 1	Yes	4	3	3	3
Therapist 2	NA	3	5	2	1
Therapist 3	NA	3	3	4	2
Therapist 4	No	3	2	2	1
Therapist 5	Yes	3	3	3	2
Therapist 6	NA	2	4	3	4
Therapist 7	Yes	3	4	4	4
Therapist 8	No	3	3	3	4
Therapist 9	Yes	4	5	4	3
Therapist 10	Yes	3	3	3	3
Therapist 11	Yes	4	5	4	3
Therapist 12	Yes	4	3	4	4
Therapist 13	Yes	3	3	3	3
Therapist 14	No	4	3	2	2
Therapist 15	No	2	2	3	2
Therapist 16	Yes	1	1	1	1
Therapist 17	No	3	3	3	4
Therapist 18	Yes	3	3	4	3

Therapist 19	No	3	4	4	3
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Appendix C-2: Parents' Responses for how Children deal with Emotional Regulation

Please refer to Appendix B-5 for full questions.

Participant #	Specified Therapy	Emotional Outbursts	Unexpected changes in Routine	Use of Self-Soothing Behaviors	Calming down after Upsetness
Participant 1	Other	NA	5	1	5
Participant 2	Other	2	5	2	3
Participant 3	Other	3	3	4	3
Participant 4	Other	2	3	4	4
Participant 5	Other	2	4	2	4
Participant 6	MT Only	1	3	4	4
Participant 7	MT + CBI	3	4	4	4
Participant 8	Other	4	2	3	2
Participant 9	MT Only	5	1	4	1
Participant 10	MT + CBI	4	5	4	3
Participant 11	MT + CBI	4	5	4	3
Participant 12	MT Only	3	4	3	5

Appendix C-3: Parents' Responses for how Children deal with Social Interaction

Please refer to Appendix B-6 for full questions.

Participants #	Specified Therapy	Reaction to Loud Noises, Bright Lights, or Physical Touch	Eye contact during Social Interactions	Social cues, facial expressions, etc.	Level of Comfort in Group Activities	Extent of Initiating Conversation
Participant 1	Other	2	4	2	3	2
Participant 2	Other	3	4	3	4	5
Participant 3	Other	3	3	3	3	2
Participant 4	Other	1	3	4	4	3
Participant 5	Other	3	3	2	2	4
Participant 6	MT Only	2	4	3	5	4
Participant 7	MT + CBI	3	3	3	3	3
Participant 8	Other	4	2	2	2	1
Participant 9	MT Only	5	1	1	1	1
Participant 10	MT + CBI	4	3	3	4	5
Participant 11	MT + CBI	3	4	3	4	5
Participant 12	MT Only	3	3	4	5	3